

Impact of ERP systems on work and work-life

Wickramasinghe, V.

Karunasekara, M.

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

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Purpose - To empirically identify the post-implementation impact of enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems on work and work-life of managerial-level end-users in terms of problem solving support, job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality, authority and decision rights, and overall impact on organization in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach - Survey methodology was used and managerial-level end-users that fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study, responded. The hypothesized relationships were examined using structural equation modelling.

Findings - It was found that “ERP system product performance” significantly predicts “Problem solving support”, “Job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality”, and “Impact on organization”. However, the direct link between “ERP system product performance” and “Authority and decision rights” is not significant.

Originality/value - The literature suggests that the impact of ERP systems on individuals and organizations can be conceptualized in terms of individual users’ perceptions and beliefs about the changes occurred after the implementation. However, the main shortcoming of past studies is that they included a limited number of consequences of ERP adoption in a single study.

Key words: Enterprise resource planning systems; ERP; product performance; Human dimension.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

Many organizations all over the world have implemented ERP systems over the past years. Motivation behind these investments is to improve organizational efficiency, effectiveness, and ultimately the performance (Beheshti and Beheshti, 2010; van Sinderen and Almeida, 2011). Yet, the understanding of how both organizations and individuals within these organizations are affected and how benefits are actually materialised have received little attention (see Arnold, 2006; Gattiker and Goodhue, 2005; Jacobs and Bendoly, 2003; Morris and Venkatesh, 2010). Further, as little research has been directed to investigate behavioural aspects of ERP systems, for this study we have drawn literature not only from ERP (such as Morris and Venkatesh, 2010) but also from manufacturing resource planning (such as Ang et al., 2002), enterprise systems (such as Arnold, 2006), information systems (such as DeLone and McLean, 2003), information technology (such as Davis, 1989) and electronic data processing/computer technology (such as Doll et al., 1994). Therefore, in this article, the terms such as ERP, enterprise systems, information systems, etc are used interchangeably.

According to the literature, with the implementation of an enterprise system (ES), organizational change is inevitable and individuals who work in these organizations will be affected differently, and consequently, different employment user groups can have differing experience of the system (Arnold, 2006). Therefore, user perspective is an important design consideration in the evaluation of information systems (IS) (Amoako-Gyampah, 2007; Calisir and Calisir, 2004; Morris and Venkatesh, 2010). In this regard, the literature identifies four different information end-users in an organization, namely, operational, technical, management, and strategic (Anthony, 1965; Doll et al., 1994; Shang and Seddon, 2002). The current study is confined to investigate the impact of ERP systems on managerial-level end-users. Scholars (such as Anthony, 1965; Doll et al., 1994; Shang and Seddon, 2002) identify managerial-level end-users as those who involved in management control in an organization by assuring that resources are obtained and used effectively and efficiently in the accomplishment of an organization's objectives.

The novelty of the current study lies in several aspects. First, although the literature emphasizes the importance of examining the effects of IS at individual and organizational levels, a limited number of empirical studies examined these effects (see Petter *et al.*, 2008). Second, empirical studies that evaluated the impact of IS mainly conceptualized the impact on individuals in terms of information awareness, information understanding, learning accurate interpretation, decision effectiveness, and improved individual productivity (see DeLone and McLean, 1992, p. 76). However, some empirical studies suggest that the impact of ERP systems can be conceptualized in terms of individual users' perceptions and beliefs about the changes occurred after the implementation (e.g. El Amrani *et al.*, 2006; Jaspersen *et al.*, 2002; Larsen, 2009; Morris and Venkatesh, 2010; Sia *et al.*, 2002). The main shortcoming of such empirical studies is that they included a limited number of consequences of ERP system adoption, such as cross-functionality (e.g. El Amrani *et al.*, 2006), in a single study. Therefore, it is reasonable to analyze the impact of ERP systems within an extended framework at the individual level. Finally, the literature suggests that although some of the changes occurred (such as decision making) as a result of ES implementation at operational and technical levels are fairly evident from the previous research, the impact on managerial-level end-users is not quite clear (see Arnold, 2006; Pinsonneault and Kraemer, 1993; Scapens and Jazayeri, 2003). Therefore, the current study focuses on the impact of ERP usage on managerial-level users.

The specific objectives of the study were to investigate the perceptions of managerial-level end-users on (a) ERP system product performance, and (b) post-implementation impact of ERP usage on them in terms problem solving support, job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality, authority and decision rights, and overall impact on organization. It is expected that the findings of this study would provide valuable information not only to academics but also to practitioners. It is also expected that the findings will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

ERP system product performance

In the current study, the term ERP system product performance is used to refer to the goodness of the application. The literature suggests that ERP system product performance should be evaluated by general employee end-users (e.g. Amoako-Gyampah, 2007; Calisir and Calisir, 2004). A large number of studies were conducted to identify dimensions that contribute to IS product performance at the end-user level (e.g. Davis, 1989; DeLone and McLean, 1992 and 2003; Doll et al., 1994; Ives *et al.*, 1983; Sengupta and Zviran, 1997; Somers *et al.*, 2003; Wu and Wang, 2006). Table 1 summarises some of the frequently used such dimensions.

As different researchers used different dimensions to evaluate IS, making comparisons become difficult. To overcome this difficulty, DeLone and McLean (2003) presented an integrated view by identifying IS dimensions under system quality, information quality, and service quality. Some of the system quality characteristics are the ease of use, system flexibility, system reliability, the ease of learning, and system features such as response time (DeLone and McLean, 1992, 2003; Petter *et al.*, 2008). Some of the information quality characteristics are relevance, understandability, accuracy, conciseness, completeness, and usability (DeLone and McLean, 1992; Petter *et al.*, 2008). Service quality explains the quality of support users receive from IS support personnel in terms of responsiveness, accuracy, reliability, technical competence, and the empathy of staff (DeLone and McLean, 1992, 2003; Petter *et al.*, 2008). According to DeLone and McLean (2003), high system quality, information quality, and service quality may lead to more system use (e.g., the amount of use) resulting in individual and organizational productivity improvements as well as more user satisfaction/user information satisfaction. According to DeLone and McLean (2003) and Petter *et al.* (2008), Ives *et al.* (1983) provides a comprehensive multi-attribute instrument for measuring user information satisfaction; Ives *et al.* (1983) included output information measures such as format, volume, precision, accuracy, timeliness, and currency. In our study most of these measures fall under the term “ERP system product performance” (refer to Table 1 and 2).

Further, the literature suggests that there is no pre-agreed set and/or a number of dimensions to evaluate ERP system product performance (see Petter *et al.*, 2008). For instance, many research studies used only one or two surrogates to evaluate product performance (e.g. Ang *et al.*, 2002; also refer to Petter *et al.*, 2008, p. 256). Some studies used a global item to evaluate product performance (e.g. Bendoly and Jacobs, 2004). In this regard, Petter *et al.* (2008) emphasize the need of using multidimensional measures in the IS research. As detailed in the section on “measures”, a multi-item measure was developed for the study based on the literature reviewed above. Table 2 provides a brief description for the dimensions used to evaluate ERP product performance in this study.

Take in Table 1

Take in Table 2

Impact of ERP system on work and work-life in organizations

New technologies operate as an external agent capable of transforming organizations and influencing behaviour and social relationships that the organizational members have subsequent to the implementation of ERP systems (Arnold, 2006; Jaspersen *et al.*, 2002). Although Petter *et al.* (2008, p. 257) emphasize the importance of focusing on individual and organizational levels in the IS research, they conclude that “careful parsing of studies by context shows that there are really insufficient data to evaluate relationships at individual and organizational levels”. Table 3 summarises some of the previous studies that highlighted the post-implementation impact of IS on work and work-life in organizations within the domain of the current study. For the study, we used the term “impact of ERP on work and work-life in organizations” to refer to the post-implementation impact of ERP systems on managerial-level end-users in terms of problem solving support, job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality, authority and decision rights, and overall impact on organization. Table 4

provides a brief description for the dimensions used to evaluate the post-implementation impact of ERP on work and work-life in organizations in this study.

Take in Table 3

Take in Table 4

Post-implementation impact of ERP on problem solving support. Past studies revealed that ERP systems enable organizations to achieve decision support benefits such as improved knowledge processing, enhanced decision making reliability, and increased ability to gather corporate evidence to support the decisions made (refer to Table 3). DeLone and McLean (1992 and 2003) used the term individual impact to explain the effect of information on the recipient by giving the recipient a better understanding of the decision context, improving his/her decision-making productivity, producing a change in recipient's decision behaviour, or changing the decision maker's perception of importance/usefulness of IS.

In the context of managerial-level end-users, past studies provide evidence that the richness of information provided by the system allows them to uncover details that were not previously known but are relevant in making decisions (see Ellis, 1984; Pinsonneault and Kraemer, 1993). Managerial-level end-users, therefore, make better decisions and analyze more alternatives in greater depth than before.

Overall, the literature reviewed above suggests that ERP product performance positively impact on problem solving support. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H1: ERP system product performance positively impact on problem solving support.

Post-implementation impact of ERP on job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality. Previous studies suggest (refer to Table 3) that ES call for a considerable degree of cross-functional co-operation and after the implementation of an ERP system the

organization is built around a partition-free horizontal structure and multi-functional work teams. Hence, users in the new organization should be aware and adapt to the interdependencies and information sharing between various organizational units (El Amrani *et al.*, 2006, Gattiker and Goodhue, 2005).

Further, the inherent design of ERP gives more job discretion to users. On the one hand, the process orientation of software promotes greater cross-functional integration. This ability to integrate front-end and back-end operations often results in greater task concentration, i.e., expanding one's job scope (Sia *et al.*, 2002, p.26). On the other hand, the process orientation of software expands access to information, allowing employees greater flexibility in doing their jobs and in shifting their work priorities, and also allowing them to make decisions that used to be formally referred upward or to other departments due to the lack of information (Sia *et al.*, 2002, p.26).

Furthermore, because information contained in the system is captured on a real-time basis and immediately available, users have continuous access to monitor their own performance as well as their subordinates' and peers' work performance on an on-going basis (Bélanger and Crossler, 2011; Scapens and Jazayeri, 2003; Spears and Lea, 1994). Hence, the changes occurred after the implementation of ERP represent fundamental changes in the way people do their jobs.

Overall, the literature reviewed above suggests that ERP product performance positively impact on job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H2: ERP system product performance positively impact on job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality.

Post-implementation impact of ERP on authority and decision rights.

The studies based on the premise that investment in IT alters information processing capabilities of a firm and formal decision making structures theorised and empirically examined the ways in which the use of IT alters the exercise and distribution of power (refer to

Table 3). For instance, Knox *et al.* (2007) and Scapens and Jazayeri (2003) suggest that the integration, standardization, routinization, and centralization that result from the implementation of an ERP system open up opportunities as well as changes within an organization that influence the exercise and distribution of power.

Further, its ability to integrate front-end and back-end operations often results in greater task concentration by expanding one's job scope. According to Sia *et al.* (2002, p. 26) "the expanded job scope could make jobs of some employees more significant or powerful than before".

Furthermore, it is highlighted that "the process-oriented design expands access to information, allowing employees greater flexibility in doing their jobs and in shifting their work priorities, and also allowing them to make decisions that used to be formally referred upward or to other departments due to lack of information" (Sia *et al.* 2002, p.26). In this regard, some studies (Ellis, 1984; Jaspersen *et al.*, 2002; Pinsonneault and Kraemer, 1993) provide evidence that ES lead to a greater equality of participation in decision making for low-status participants.

Therefore, subsequent to the investment in IS there would be a considerable reduction of power, authority and decision rights enjoyed by managerial-level end-users. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H3: ERP system product performance negatively impact on authority and decision rights.

Post-implementation impact of ERP on the organization as a whole. Several past research investigated the effects of IS on organizations (refer to Table 3). DeLone and McLean (1992 and 2003) used the term organizational impact to explain the effect of IS on organizational performance. In this regard, Mason (1978) proposed a hierarchy of influence levels in an organization from the receipt of the information, through the understanding of the information, the application of the information to a specific problem, and the change in decision behaviour to a resultant change in organizational performance.

Several previous laboratory experiments also provide evidence that the use of IS influence to reduce production, inventory or purchasing costs, increase strategic decision-making capabilities, increase organization's revenue and profit, and return on investment (refer to DeLone and McLean, 1992). Petter *et al.* (2008) used the term net benefits to explain "the extent to which the system is contributing to the success of individuals, groups, organizations, industries, and nations" (p. 239).

Overall, the literature reviewed above suggests that ERP product performance positively impact on the organization as a whole. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H4: ERP system product performance positively impact on organization.

Figure 1 shows the proposed relationships for the study.

Take in Figure 1

Research methods

Measures

All the measures were on a five-point Likert scale where 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. The item measures used for the study are shown in Table 5. Where available, scale items from previous research studies were used. For the constructs that did not have readily available scale items, appropriate scale items were developed. Cronbach's alpha reliability of measurement scales were examined and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) were conducted following the recommended guidelines (see Hair *et al.*, 2006).

Take in Table 5

ERP system product performance. The seven-item measure had a Cronbach's alpha reliability of .875 and factor analysis yielded one factor. The results of CFA and EFA are provided in Table 6. According to Hair *et al.* (2006), factor loadings must be interpreted considering practical and statistical significance. With regard to practical significance, Hair *et al.* (2006, p. 152) suggest that factor loadings of .5 or greater are considered as practically significant. With regard to statistical significance, Hair *et al.* (2006, p. 152, Table 3.2) provide a guideline for identifying significant factor loadings based on sample size. When Hair *et al.*'s (2006, p. 152, Table 3.2) guidelines are applied to the present study, the factors loadings yielded are considered as statistically significant as well.

Take in Table 6

Impact of ERP on work and work-life in organizations. The 17-item measure had a Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.884. The factor analysis yielded a set of four factors, which explained 81.34% of the variance. These four factors were labelled as "Problem solving support", "Job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality", "Authority and decision rights", and "Impact on organization". The results of CFA and EFA are provided in Table 7. Based on the criteria discussed above (see Hair *et al.*, 2006, p. 152), the factor loadings are considered as practically and statistically significant. Although Fornell and Larker (1981) suggest that statistically convergent constructs should have AVE above .5, we decided to retain the factor "Authority and decision rights" with an AVE of .47 considering the practical importance of this construct.

Take in Table 7

Respondents' level of participation in the ERP system and the degree of understanding of the ERP system. Two items were used to measure respondents' level of participation in and the degree of understanding of the ERP system (refer to Table 9).

Sample

The list of firms that implemented ERP systems was obtained from a firm that conducted a comprehensive independent market survey on ERP systems in use in Sri Lanka. The evaluation of the list suggested that the majority of firms belong to the manufacturing sector have implemented ERP compared to any other business sectors. In order to obtain a homogeneous sample of firms, we confined our sample to manufacturing firms that have implemented ERP systems.

A sample of private sector manufacturing firms was identified from the list that fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study, i.e., 1) business performance of the firms, and 2) the use of ERP system should be mandatory and it should be functioning for at least one year. About 20 firms fulfilled the criteria of which 15 firms willingly participated in this study. Contact persons from each firm were instructed to distribute the self-administered survey questionnaire to a randomly selected group of managerial-level end-users throughout their organizations (from production, sales and distribution, HR, financial, etc. depending on the nature of modules implemented) (refer to Table 8). Participants were briefed the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution and they completed the questionnaire anonymously. Of the 150 questionnaires distributed, 100 valid responses were yielded. Hence, the response rate was 67% of the original sample. The profile of the firms and respondents are shown in Table 8.

Take in Table 8

Data collection and analysis

When self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights the problem of common method bias (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003; Spector 1994).

Procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias in the current study. First, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension (a procedure recommended by Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). Second, factor analysis was used to conduct Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff *et al.* (2003).

The hypothesized relationships were examined by means of structural equation modelling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation using AMOS 16 (refer to Table 11). SEM technique facilitates the simultaneous estimation of multiple interrelated dependence relationships of the dimensions (see Hair *et al.*, 2006, p. 776). Our study fulfilled the criteria stipulated for SEM by Hair *et al.* (2006, p. 766).

Results

The responses to the respondents' level of participation in the ERP system and the degree of understanding of the system are shown in Table 9. When the use of a system is mandatory, the extent of use conveys little information about the system (see Petter *et al.*, 2008). Further, DeLone and McLean (2003) state that even in the mandatory systems, there can still be considerable variability of use. Since the use is mandatory in the firms studied, this information is not taken into further analysis but taken to describe as a characteristic of the sample.

Take in Table 9

Table 10 shows the descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations between variables. The square root of AVE for each construct is also shown in Table 10. As the square root of AVE for a given construct is greater than the correlation between that construct and all other constructs, the discriminant validity seems adequate.

Take in Table 10

Fit measures of Chi-square, GFI, CFI, and RMSEA were used to evaluate the structural model (see Hair *et al.* 2006, p. 776). The structural model achieved a good level of fit having CMIN/df = 2.431, CFI = 0.91 and RMSEA = 0.04 (see Hair *et al.* 2006).

Figure 2 shows the research model derived through structural equation modelling with standardised path loadings. The summary of the results is provided in Table 11. As can be seen from Table 11, positive significant relationships “problem solving support” (H1), “job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality” (H2), and “impact on organization” (H4) have with “ERP system product performance” support hypotheses 1, 2 and 4. As the negative relationship between “Authority and decision rights” and “ERP system product performance” is not significant, H3 is not supported by the data.

Further, as shown in Table 11, the coefficient of determination (squared multiple correlation) of .651 suggests that “ERP system product performance” accounts for 65% of the variation of “impact on organization”. Further, the coefficient of determination of .386 suggests that “ERP system product performance” accounts for 39% of the variation of “problem solving support”. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination of .310 suggests that “ERP system product performance” accounts for 31% of the variation of “job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality”..

Furthermore, as shown in Figure 2 and Table 11, path analysis showed that the link between “problem solving support” and “impact on organization” is significant. Hence, in addition to the direct effect “ERP system product performance” has with “impact on

organization”, there is an indirect effect of “ERP system product performance” through “problem solving support”.

Take in Figure 2

Take in Table 11

Discussion and conclusions

Enterprise resource planning systems represent the latest and most ambitious application of administrative and computer-based technologies in IS and the implementation of an ERP system leads to organizational transformation. However, a few empirical studies have investigated the post-implementation impact of ERP on work and work-life in organizations. The current study investigated the post-implementation impact of ERP from managerial-level end-users’ perspective. The main intention of the study was to investigate the ways in which ERP system product performance impacts on work and work-life in organizations.

With regard to conceptualizing the term “impact of IS on individuals”, several researchers conceptualized the term by way of individuals’ perceptions and beliefs toward IS after using it to perform job related tasks (e.g. El Amrani *et al.*, 2006). Such researchers found, on the one hand, that IS provides useful information, which improves individuals’ decision-making capabilities (Wu and Wang, 2006). Some other researchers found, on the other hand, that IS influences individuals’ beliefs towards, for instance, the distribution of power within the workplace (e.g. Sia *et al.*, 2002). Such empirical studies highlight the need of evaluating the impact of IS through various dimensions such as job discretion, management visibility, power and authority (e.g. Jaspersen *et al.*, 2002). The current study investigated the impact of ERP systems on individuals’ work and work-life in organizations in terms of problem solving support, job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality, authority and decision rights, and overall impact on organization that are until recently had been studied separately, in a single study.

With regard to the call for a need of valid and reliable multidimensional measurement scales for predicting the influence of IS (Davis, 1989; Petter *et al.*, 2008), we have used widely accepted multiple dimensions drawn from the literature that are relevant for our study (such as Somers *et al.*, 2003) to evaluate the ERP system product performance. The 7-item measure used in this study was empirically based and was shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context. Similarly, we have drawn item measures to evaluate the impact of ERP system on work and work-life from the literature (such as El Amrani *et al.*, 2006); these were shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context.

The study found that “ERP system product performance” significantly predicts “problem solving support”, “job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality”, and “impact on organization”. With regard to the impact of ERP system on problem solving support, a key feature of an ERP system is the integrated central database, which collects data from, and feeds data into modular applications supporting virtually all of an organization’s business activities across functions, across business units and across the world. When new information is entered in one place, related information is then automatically updated. Hence, the ERP system provides integrated real time decision information. Because the ERP system ensures that all levels of planning are based on the same data and that the resulting plans realistically reflect the prevailing operating conditions of the firm, the findings revealed a significant link between “ERP product performance” and “problem solving support”. With regard to the impact of ERP system on “job discretion, management visibility, and cross-functionality”, the findings of our study support the findings of previous studies that revealed ERP product performance increases job discretion and procedural formality (e.g. Sia *et al.*, 2002), cross-functional integration (e.g. El Amrani *et al.*, 2006), and management visibility (e.g. Sia *et al.*, 2002). With regard to the impact of ERP system on “authority and decision rights”, although previous research found that ERP systems influence authority and decision rights (e.g. Jaspersen *et al.*, 2002) the findings from our study do not support this link significantly. With regard to the impact of ERP system on the organization as a whole, it was found that ERP system product performance has a significant positive effect on the

organization. This finding supports the findings of earlier studies (such as DeLone and McLean, 2003; Knox *et al.*, 2007) that revealed IS eventually has some impact on the organization.

Past studies that investigated the effect of information on the behaviour of the recipient, termed individual impact, conceptualized the impact as "improving my - or my department's - performance", and provided evidence that the information system has had a positive impact by giving the user a better understanding of the decision context (e.g. DeLone and McLean, 1992, p. 69). Further, Pinsonneault and Kraemer (1993) and Ellis (1984) found that the richness of information provided by the system provides managerial-level end-users' with information that were not previously known but are relevant in making decisions and allows them to make better decisions and analyse more alternatives in a greater depth than before. The findings of the current study, therefore, support the findings of earlier studies that the ERP system provides integrated decision information (e.g. Petter *et al.*, 2008).

In developing the research model (refer to Figure 1) we hypothesized direct relationships between ERP system product performance and the dependent variables. As hypothesized, we found significant direct relationships between "ERP system product performance" and "problem solving support", "job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality", and "impact on organization". In addition to these significant direct relationships, we found an indirect effect of "ERP system product performance" on "impact on organization" through "problem solving support" (refer to Figure 2). Further, the findings of our study also suggest that although the link between "ERP system product performance" and "job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality" is significant, the link between "job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality" and "impact on organization" is not significant. Furthermore, the findings suggest that the link between "ERP system product performance" and "authority and decision rights" as well as the link between "authority and decision rights" and "impact on organization" is not significant. As we have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated these relationships, this warrants future research.

Implications

The findings have implications for both theory and practice. With regard to the contribution of the study for the literature, although there are empirical studies available that investigated one side of our framework (i.e., either ERP system product performance or impact of ERP on work and work-life) empirical research studies that investigated the link between these two areas are rare. We have not come across previous empirical research that investigated post-implementation impact of ERP on work and work-life in organizations, in general or specific to a particular user group (e.g. managerial-level end-users), in the literature. Therefore, the findings of our study make a contribution to the literature. However, a considerable future research is needed to test our propositions and to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results presented in this article. Yet, we believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

With regard to the contribution of the study for the practice, the specific literature on ERP suggests that changes subsequent to the ERP implementation are not quite clear (see Arnold, 2006). Therefore, first, the findings of this study would contribute for practitioners to better understand the managerial-level end-users' perceptions towards ERP system product performance and the consequences of ERP usage for them in terms of problem solving support, job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality, authority and decision rights, and overall impact on organization. This becomes important as more and more organizations implement ERP systems and empirical research addressing these human dimensions in this area is presently lacking.

Second, specifically, the significant positive relationship between ERP system product performance and job discretion, management visibility, and cross-functionality implies that the ERP system allows management to assign work directly to subordinates and to follow-up the progress; to rely a great deal on subordinates to ensure proper operation and processing when they use the system; to become aware of how individual actions and outcomes affect the entire organization; and to create and reinforce a sense of community across all units of

the organization. Third, the non-significant relationship between ERP system product performance and authority and decision rights implies that individuals do not perceive that their authority in decision making is reduced by the ERP system, they do not perceive that power resides not in people but in the system, and they do not perceive that their ability to own and control resources (including information) is challenged by the ERP system. These implications (second and third mentioned above) may provide new insights for practitioners (and academics) as past empirical research seldom addressed ERP's post-implementation impact on both "job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality" and "authority and decision rights" from system end-users' perspective, especially, from managerial-level end-users' perspective.

Fourth, the findings imply that the impact of ERP on work and work-life of organizations is a multidimensional construct (problem solving support, job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality, authority and decision rights, and impact on organization). The four factors are interwoven, and one must not focus exclusively on any single factor in assessing the influence of ERP.

Finally, academics and practitioners can employ "problem solving support", "job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality", "authority and decision rights", and "impact on organization" as measures to study the impact of ERP on work and work-life in organizations. This will enhance the understanding of the extent of ERP system product performance and how it influences the dimensionality of work and work-life in organizations. Once this understanding is gained, necessary actions could be taken not only to improve ERP system product performance, but also to improve positive effects or to reduce any negative effects of ERP on work and work-life in organizations. Therefore, the measures proposed in this study could be used to serve as a diagnostic tool to assess and analyse issues in connection to the usage of ERP systems and could take necessary corrective actions to improve them.

Future research areas

With regard to areas for future research, first, the validity of a measure cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional study. The validation of a measure requires the assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. Hence, future research, in different samples and longitudinal studies, are necessary that compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews. Second, from the organizational perspective, the implementation of an ERP system encounter resistance since the implementation usually requires people to create new job relationships, share information, and make decisions that they have never made before. The presence of distinct frames of reference among people who work in different functions can lead to conflicting expectations and decrease productivity. Therefore, future studies could investigate the influence of differences between functions and personal cultural differences in the way work processes are interpreted even though there is some degree of cross-functional integration.

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Figures

Figure 1. Proposed research model

Figure 2. Structural equation model results

Note: ***p<.001

NS = Non-significant paths.

Tables

Table 1. ERP system product performance

Measure	Timeliness of output	Relevancy of output	Accuracy of output	Reliability of output	Precision of output	Completeness of output	Response time/saves time	Clarity of output format	Convenience of access
Related literature									
Barki (1990)	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
DeLone and McLean (1992, 2003)	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Doll et al. (1994)	√	√	√	√					
Ives et al. (1983)		√	√		√	√			
Sengupta and Zviran (1997)		√	√	√	√	√			
Somers <i>et al.</i> (2003)	√	√	√	√				√	
Wu and Wang (2006)	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√

Table 2: Dimensions used to evaluate ERP product performance

Term	Description
Timeliness of output information	Output information is available at a time suitable for its use
Relevancy of output information	Congruence between user tasks and system functions
Accuracy of output information	Correctness of output information
Reliability of output information	Output information is consistent and dependable
Precision of output information	System provides precise information
Completeness of output information	Comprehensiveness of output information
Response time	Elapsed time between user request and a reply from the system
Clarity of output format	Output information is clear and understandable
Convenience of access	Convenience access to information

Table 3. Post-implementation impact on work and work-life

Related literature	Impact	Decision making/ problem solving	Power/ authority/ resource control	Job discretion/ procedural formality	Management visibility/peer visibility/system tracking capability	Cross-functionality/ cross-functional integration	Impact on organization
Astley and Sachdeva (1984)			√				
Beheshti and Beheshti, (2010)							√
Bendoly <i>et al.</i> (2006)						√	
Bloomfield and Coombs (1992)			√				
Bradshaw-Camball and Murray (1991)			√				
DeLone and McLean (1992, 2003)	√						√
El Amrani <i>et al.</i> (2006)						√	
Gattiker and Goodhue (2005)	√					√	√
Jasperson <i>et al.</i> (2002)			√				
Kallunki <i>et al.</i> (2011)							√
Knox <i>et al.</i> (2007)	√		√				
Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall (2006)						√	
Rhodes <i>et al.</i> (2011)							√
Scapens and Jazayeri (2003)				√			
Sewell (1998)					√		
Shang and Seddon (2002)							√
Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002)				√	√		√
Sillince and Mouakket (1998)			√				
Spears and Lea (1994)					√		
Spreitzer (1995)				√			
Tjahjono (2009)	√						
Wu and Wang (2006)	√						

Table 4: Dimensions used to evaluate post-implementation impact of ERP on work and work-life

Term	Description
Problem solving support	Usefulness in defining problems, selecting and prioritizing problems and in forming solutions
Decision making support	Usefulness of the information product in making decisions
Authority	Power associated with information and expertise as the base
Resource control	Power derived from the ability to control supply of resources to others
Job discretion	Autonomy in deciding how to carry out work
Procedural formality	Clarity of procedures spelled out to carry out a task
Management visibility	Information in the system can be used by a supervisor to see the status of his/her subordinates' work performance
Peer visibility	Information in the system can be viewed by a person to see the status of his/her peers' work performance
System tracking capability	System provides information on how well or badly a person carried out tasks
Cross-functionality	Awareness of interdependencies and information sharing between various organizational units
Cross-functional integration	Ability to integrate front-end and back-end operations with greater task concentration
Impact on organization	Effect of information product on organizational performance

Table 5. Item measures

Item measure	Related literature
ERP system product performance:	
ERP system provides reliable information.	Ives <i>et al.</i> (1983), Doll <i>et al.</i> (1994), Somers <i>et al.</i> (2003).
ERP system provides up-to-date information.	Doll <i>et al.</i> (1994) and Somers <i>et al.</i> (2003).
ERP system provides accurate information.	Ives <i>et al.</i> (1983), Doll <i>et al.</i> (1994), Somers <i>et al.</i> (2003).
ERP System is reliable.	Calisir and Calisir (2004).
Information provided by the ERP system is very relevant to my job.	Sengupta and Zviran (1997).
ERP System is fast and saves time.	Doll <i>et al.</i> (1994) and Somers <i>et al.</i> (2003).
Information provided by the ERP system is clear and understandable.	Doll <i>et al.</i> (1994) and Somers <i>et al.</i> (2003).
Outcomes of ERP:	
I feel that my authority in decision making is reduced by the ERP system.	Bradshaw-Cambali and Murray (1991).
I feel that other people do not ask for my expertise as information is readily available in the ERP system.	Bradshaw-Cambali and Murray (1991).
I feel that my ability to own and control resources (including information) is challenged by the ERP system.	Astley and Sachdeva (1984), Sillince and Mouakket (1998).
I feel that with the ERP system, power resides not in people but in the system.	Bloomfield and Coombs (1992).
ERP system provides me information which is useful in defining problems.	Barki (1990).
ERP system provides me information which is useful in forming solutions.	Barki (1990).
ERP system provides me information which is useful in selecting and prioritising problems.	Barki (1990).
Increased control over operations gained through the ERP system helps me to make better decisions.	Developed for the current study.
ERP system created and reinforced a sense of community across all units of the organization.	Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall (2006).

With the use of the ERP system, it is very clear how my individual actions and outcomes affect the entire organization.	Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall (2006).
Because of the ERP system, I know how my work affects other functions and people.	Spreitzer (1995).
Management relies a great deal on me to ensure proper operation/processing when I use the ERP system.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
With the use of the ERP system, management can easily assign work directly to me and follow up the progress.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
With the use of the ERP system, management can easily assign work directly to my team and follow up the progress.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
I am satisfied with the service the ERP system is doing for me and my work.	Developed for the current study.
The work processes in my organization has improved after the ERP system implementation.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
ERP system has had a significant positive effect on my organization.	Gattiker and Goodhue (2005).

Table 6. Summarized results: CFA and EFA - ERP system product performance

	Factor loading
	ERP system product performance
ERP system provides reliable information	.862
ERP system provides accurate information	.855
ERP System is reliable	.769
ERP System is fast and saves time	.685
ERP system provides up-to-date information	.683
The information provided by the ERP system is clear and understandable	.653
The information provided by the ERP system is very relevant to my job	.646
Eigenvalue	4.87
Explained variation	65.51%
Cronbach's alpha	.875
AVE	.55
Construct reliability	.89

Table 7. Summarised results: CFA and EFA - impact of ERP on work and work-life in organizations

	Factor loading			
	F 1: Problem solving support	F 2: Job discretion, management visibility and cross- functionality	F 3: Impact on organization	F 4: Authority and decision rights
ERP system provides me information which is useful in forming solutions	.767	.389	.200	.092
ERP system provides me information which is useful in defining problems	.765	.033	.313	.045
Increased control over operations gained through the ERP system helps me to make better decisions	.678	.381	.213	.078
ERP system provides me information which is useful in selecting and prioritising problems	.670	.284	.120	-.006
With the use of the ERP system, management can easily assign work directly to me and follow-up the progress	.251	.874	.011	.130
With the use of the ERP system, management can easily assign work directly to my team and follow-up the progress	.287	.860	.366	-.053
Management relies a great deal on me to ensure proper operation/processing when I use the ERP system	.084	.771	.327	-.206
Because of the ERP system, I know how my work affects other functions and people	.041	.708	.180	-.124
With the usage of the ERP system, it is very clear how my individual actions and outcomes affect the entire organization	.208	.673	.129	.068
ERP system created and reinforced a sense of community across all units of the organization	.307	.643	.085	.054
The work processes in my organization has improved after the ERP system implementation	.205	.147	.861	.026
I am satisfied with the service the ERP system is doing for me and my work	.279	.285	.858	.141
ERP system has had a significant positive effect on my organization	.297	.315	.818	-.017
I feel that my authority in decision making is reduced by the ERP system	.111	-.060	-.136	.845
I feel that with the ERP system, power resides not in people but in the system	.107	.163	.091	.672
I feel that other people do not ask for my expertise as information is readily available in the ERP system	.090	-.256	.340	.609
I feel that my ability to own and control resources (including information) is challenged by the ERP system	-.121	.024	-.011	.602
Eigenvalue	5.53	3.78	2.58	1.07
Explained variation	38.57%	21.25%	15.26%	6.26%
Cronbach's alpha	.817	.881	.883	.776
AVE	.52	.58	.72	.47
Construct reliability	.81	.89	.88	.78

Note: Variables are sorted by highest loading.

Table 8. Demographic information (N=100)

<i>Industrial sector:</i>		<i>ERP use duration by the firm:</i>	
Export apparel manufacturing	65%	Less than 3 years	25%
Food, beverage and tobacco	15%	3 - 5 years	46%
Plastic, rubber and polymer	10%	More than 5 years	29%
Other	10%		
<i>Total number of employees:</i>		<i>Respondents' highest educational level:</i>	
Less than 500	16%	Postgraduate degree	18%
500 – 999	12%	Bachelors degree	64%
1,000 – 4,999	47%	Diploma	18%
5,000 – 9,999	12%		
10,000 or above	13%	<i>Gender:</i>	
		Male	84%
		Female	16%
<i>Number of employees using ERP:</i>		<i>Number of employees directly supervise:</i>	
Less than 200	52%	Less than 10	71%
200 – 499	28%	10 – 19	21%
500 or above	20%	20 or above	8%
<i>Product type:</i>		<i>Respondents' age:</i>	
Customised (developed for my firm)	19%	Less than 25 years	8%
Off-the-shelf with customizations	81%	25 – 29	41%
		30 – 34	35%
		35 or above	16%
<i>Frequently implemented modules:</i>		<i>Respondents' years of experience in the firm:</i>	
Material management	100%	Less than 3 years	22%
Production planning	100%	3 – 5 years	67%
Financial accounting	96%	More than 5 years	11%
Sales and distribution	77%		
HR	38%		
Quality management	33%		
Maintenance	29%		

Table 9. Respondents' level of participation and understanding of the ERP system

	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Respondents' level of participation in the ERP system	4.04	0.76	-.84	.02
The degree of understanding of the ERP system	3.89	0.84	-.25	.43

Table 10. Descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1. ERP system product performance	3.78	0.68	.74				
2. Problem solving support	3.66	0.60	.54**	.72			
3. Job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality	3.59	0.72	.44**	.45*	.76		
4. Authority and decision rights	2.83	0.74	-.13	.12	-.02	.69	
5. Impact on organization	3.85	0.84	.58**	.52**	.34*	.14	.85

Note: **: $p < .01$; *: $p < .05$.

Diagonal entries: square root of AVE, Off-diagonal entries: correlations between constructs.

Table 11. Summary of the results - structural model coefficients

Path	Result	Standardized regression estimate (significance) Direct effect	Standardized regression estimate Indirect effect	Squared multiple correlation
ERP system product performance ---> Authority and decision rights	Not supported	-.071 ($p > .10$)	-	.005
ERP system product performance ---> Problem solving support	Supported	.622 ($p < .001$)	-	.386
ERP system product performance ---> Job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality	Supported	.557 ($p < .001$)	-	.310
ERP system product performance ---> Impact on organization	Supported	.439 ($p < .001$)	.266	.651
Authority and decision rights ---> Impact on organization	Not supported	.044 ($p > .10$)	-	-
Problem solving support ---> Impact on organization	Supported	.492 ($p < .001$)	-	-
Job discretion, management visibility and cross-functionality ---> Impact on organization	Not supported	.066 ($p > .10$)	-	-